

ISic0772

I.Sicily inscription 0772

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

volcanic (local)

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

sporadic find of 1950 in the castle

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 761

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height 58 cm

Width 29-36.5 cm

Depth 27 cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms

The O is only 29mm high

Letter heights:

Line 1: 58-65 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: n/a mm

Text

1. Augusto

Apparatus

Text of I.Lipara

Translation (en)

To Augustus

Commentary**Digital identifiers:**

TM 175804

EDR 081547

EDCS 6100297

PHI 334858

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1989.0346b

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Bernabò Brea, L, Cavalier, M 1998. Meligunìs Lipára IX. Topografia di Lipari in età greca e romana. Palermo. At vol.1, p.150 no.24 tav.63.4

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